

**ASSESSMENT OF THE STATUS OF MEDICAL NEGLIGENCE AND
MALPRACTICE IN MUSANZE DISTRICT, RWANDA**

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**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL/FACULTY OF LAW IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF BACHELORS IN
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DECLARATION

I declare that this Dissertation contains my own original work and has not been submitted for any award anywhere else by me or any other person.

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DEDICATION

This piece of work has been devoted to my respected Family and friends for their love, care and encouragement.

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This study was made possible by the support, tolerance and constant motivation of my very supportive and patient supervisor, Mr Viateur Bangayandusha. Therefore, I am very grateful of his support.

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I wish I could list all individuals and institutions that contributed, in one way or another, to the successful completion of my study. But they are too many to mention all.

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out in Musanze District, Northern Province of Rwanda. The general objective was to assess the status of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda. Both primary and secondary data were collected. Questionnaire survey was used for primary data collection where purposive sampling was used. Secondary data were gathered from books, report, journals, magazines and internet. The collected data were analyzed by using Microsoft excel package. The majority of respondents (88%) admitted to have been involved, witnessed or dealt with medical negligence and/medical malpractices case where only 14.7% of stated that the cases were taken to court. The majority of respondents, especially patients perceive the medical negligence and malpractice as a critical issue, whereas most of respondents are moderately aware about the rights to medical care (45%) in addition to 25% of respondents who are very aware about the rights to medical care. Most of respondents (37.5%) especially the patients ignore the laws governing medical negligence and malpractice. The majority of respondents (60%) perceive the existing laws as weak while as the majority of respondents (74%) think that the existing laws are rarely applied in case of medical negligence and malpractice. The main factor contributing the medical negligence and malpractice is the “scarcity of medical practitioners” (90%) followed by “other health priorities” (80%), poor training of practitioners (54%), law deficit (50%) and public ignorance (46%). The main perceived effect of the medical negligence and malpractice on victims is the “loss of trust in medical practitioners” (100%) followed by “condition worsening” (90%), defensive medicine (62%) and psychological damages (20%). The most frequently perceived solution would be “the effort by medical practitioners to reduce harm” (74%) followed by “awareness campaign” (62%), “improved communication” (62%) and “law enforcement” (28%). The study concluded that the current situation of medical negligence and malpractice is critical. The majority of service users ignore the existing laws; the main factor contributing the medical negligence and malpractice is the “scarcity of medical practitioners”; the most frequently perceived solution to medical negligence and malpractice would be “the effort by medical practitioners to reduce harm and has recommended further researches and the empowerment of regulation organs and bodies, the organization of education and awareness campaigns about the existing laws, the increase the number of health practitioners and training of them on how to reduce harm to patients.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AMA	: American Medical Association
BC	: Before Christ
CBHI	: Community-Based Health Insurance Scheme (),
CA	: Court of Appeals
DHS	: Rwanda Demographic and Health Survey
EDPRS	: Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy
HDI	: Health Development Initiative
KMPDB	: Kenya Medical Practitioners and Dentists Board
LODA	: Local Administrative Entities Development Agency
RIB	: Rwanda Investigation Bureau
RMDC	: Rwanda Medical and Dental Council
PHC4	: Rwanda Population and Housing Census 4
WHO	: World Health Organization
SONARWA	: Société Nouvelle des Assurances du Rwanda
UK	: United Kingdom
ULR	Uganda Law Reform

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

0.1. Background of the study

In the medical world, patients consign their fate and life to doctors because they blind-trust in the doctors' knowledge and skills. And as such, society entrusts the sacred duty of preserving the qualities of life and good health to the medical professionals. Hence, only the most qualified individuals should engage in this profession. Doctors recognize and accept their great responsibility to society and have time in honoring respect imposed upon themselves. As such, where a medical professional fails to give due regard to the health and welfare of their patients as governed by their oath and the Law.¹ And deviates from the normal practice of the profession, causing injury, damage or death, may thus amount to medical negligence.²

The Hippocratic Oath is an oath taken by doctors swearing to practice medicine ethically. It is widely believed to have been written by Hippocrates, the father of western medicine, in Ionic Greek late 5th century BC. Hippocratic Oath hastens the moral conduct of physicians, assuming the respect for all human life, even the unborn. Medical profession is one of the oldest professions of the world and is the most humanitarian one. Inherent in the concept of any profession is a code of conduct, containing the basic ethics that underline the moral values that govern professional practice and is aimed at upholding its dignity.³

Medical negligence has been defined as “the omission to do something which a reasonable man would do or doing something which a reasonable man would not do in order to protect another person from a foreseeable risk of harm”.⁴ Medical neglect is the failure to provide medical, dental, or psychiatric care that is necessary to prevent or to treat serious physical or emotional injury or illness.⁵ Medical Ethics underpins the values at the heart of the practitioner-client relationship.

¹ Law n^o49/2012 Of 22/01/2013 establishing medical professional liability insurance.

² ULR, 2017 accessed on 5th may 2021

³ Mukama, H.E, 2010

⁴ Black's Law Dictionary

⁵ ULR, 2017 accessed on 5th may 2021

Medical negligence and malpractices by doctors are grey areas in health care where legal issues arise as it is in the law N° 44/2012 of 14/01/2013; Law on the organization, functioning and competence of the Medical and Dental Council⁶. Medical malpractice occurs where a medical practitioner acts in a negligent manner when treating a medical condition or deviates from accepted standards of practice in the medical community and causes injury or death to the patient. There are some errors which does not provide clear responsibility of the health professionals which are excusable errors, and others which provides the liability to the health professionals like; health risk and medical harm, and the patients (victims) have the rights to sue for compensation when they provide the casual link between the risks and the medical procedure established.

If courts make findings of negligence on delicate evidence doctors are likely to protect themselves by what has become known as defensive medicine.⁷ Defensive medicine is widespread and takes many forms within a doctor's practice, including ordering unnecessary diagnostic imagery; unnecessarily issuing referrals, over documentation of clinical notes, prescribing more medication than needed and recommending invasive procedures against professional judgment.⁸

Defensive medicine causes low-value care, that is, care that confers little or no benefit and instead may cause harm to patients. This behavior leads to higher rates of over diagnosis and overtreatment. Over diagnosis occurs when individuals are diagnosed with a disease that will not negatively affect them during the course of their life nor cause early mortality. However, only a small portion of patients benefit from the detection. Doctors, who issue referrals or send patients off for unnecessary tests or procedures, 'just in case', can trigger a cascade of unnecessary sequential tests and incidental findings, rarely amounting to any clinical importance that creates greater legal risks for doctors, by unnecessarily subjecting patients to possible harms and complications.⁹

⁶ Official website of the Rwanda medical and dental council

⁷ Contemporary Healthcare Context: Current Trends and Harms of Defensive Medicine

⁸ Contemporary Healthcare Context: Current Trends and Harms of Defensive Medicine

⁹ Contemporary Healthcare Context: Current Trends and Harms of Defensive Medicine

The patient or any other health service user shall have the right to refuse treatment or any medical procedure, to withdraw consent during treatment or to refuse the continuation of the medical procedure performed on him/her. Refusal of treatment or withdrawal of consent shall be made in writing and documented in the patient's medical record.¹⁰ The exception is provided in case of emergency, any necessary intervention may only be performed, in the interests of the patient, after favorable opinion from another competent health professional or from the management of the health facility where health care services are being provided.¹⁰

The government of Rwanda has been at the forefront of instating laws and regulations aimed at protecting the rights of the Rwandan people against poor quality services in a wide range of public and private sector service domains. The charter of patients from the Ministry of Health provides that all Rwandans, regardless of gender, sexual orientation, age, religion, cultural belief or handicap, are equally entitled to receive health services to promote and maintain good health.¹¹ In 2013, the government, in consultation with its health sector partners, established the Law establishing medical professional liability insurance law N° 49/2012 of 22/01/2013¹², which instituted medical professional liability insurance. This law elaborates medical service users' rights and the responsibilities of health service providers. Doctors have a duty to inform patients of all material risks and provide adequate advice and information, additionally they must take all appropriate steps to facilitate a diagnosis and take notice of patient concerns.¹³

Doctors may be held liable for a missed or delayed diagnosis, and it identifies compensation benefits for health care users who, due to medical service(s) that was provided to them, were rendered incapable of leading the life they used to live prior to receiving care.¹⁴ Unfortunately, most service users lack knowledge of their legal rights, which hinders improvement of service quality. This barrier to delivering quality services has been noted by several organizations, including the government of Rwanda. Cases of medical negligence have become a common occurrence in Rwanda causing damages, injury and death.¹⁵

¹⁰ Art 10 of Law n°49/2012 of 22/01/2013 establishing medical professional liability insurance

¹¹ HDI, 2013 accessed on 5th may 2021

¹² Official website of the Rwanda medical and dental council last accessed on 5th May 2021

¹³ General Principles of Medical Negligence and Background of the Civil Liability

¹⁴ HDI, 2013.

¹⁵ Prof.Justin, 2014

This study is intended to investigate medical negligence occurrences in Rwanda and propose legislative and non-legislative interventions to remedy the situation. This part of the study covers the background, the problem statement, the justifications, the objectives, the scope and duration of the study. Specific objectives will include evaluating the current situation of medical negligence in Rwanda, to assess the medical service users' knowledge of legal rights with according challenges and propose according mitigation measures. Increased awareness of these rights would have a positive impact on users' ability to demand that their rights be respected, which could subsequently ensure quality health care service delivery.

0.2. Scope of the study

This research was limited into three limitations as follow; in domain, this research is in Law of obligation as it deals with the duties and obligation of doctors and the Law n0 49/2012 of 22/01/2013 establishing medical professional liability insurance. In space, this is a localized research conducted in one District, Musanze; Northern Rwanda. The selection of this study district has been guided by its proximity to the University and the place of residence of the researcher. In time this research is limited on a period of 09 years, from 2013, a period corresponding to the establishment of the law N° 49/2012 of 22/01/2013, establishing medical professional liability insurance.

0.3. Statement of the problem

Certain relationships between two parties attract a legal duty of care to be owed from one individual to the other, to avoid reasonably foreseeable harm. For a claim in negligence to succeed a plaintiff must prove a duty of care was owed and subsequently breached by the defendant, by reason of failing to take reasonable care and as a result the plaintiff has suffered an injury or damage. The duty of care between doctors and their patients is settled within tort law and accordingly, is rarely disputed within cases.¹⁶

¹⁶General Principles of Medical Negligence and Background of the Civil Liability

There seems to be a trend of claims of medical malpractice going unreported with the patients only sharing this kind of information in other forums other than the regulatory body of medical practitioners or the courts. Despite the Act containing quite elaborate provisions on disciplinary measures, cases of medical malpractice have been on the increase in the recent past. 53 medical litigation cases were identified in Rwanda from 2008 to 2013. In essence there are many silent potential cases of medical malpractice which have not been addressed mainly because the victims either do not have confidence in the professional regulatory bodies or are scared of the procedures and complexities associated with the court process.¹⁷

The Ministry of Health provides that all Rwandans, regardless of gender, sexual orientation, age, religion, cultural belief or handicap, are equally entitled to receive health services to promote and maintain good health. Patients also have a right to complain if services delivered are not up to standard. Law N°30/2001 of 12/116/2001 creating the Medical Council is the only instrument that so far provides deterrent measures to medical malpractice in Rwanda. One of the responsibilities of the Council is to punish doctors' offences whenever they are likely to abuse the honor or dignity of the medical profession³

The law imposes a higher standard of care on professionals than that of an ordinary person, due to their special knowledge and skills. The level of expertise varies between general and specialist medical practitioners and as a result, there are varying the degrees of standard of care required at law. Although the court has the ultimate discretion in determining the standard of care more often than not, the court will be guided by expert opinion. The inclusion of 'widely accepted professional opinion' within the statute seeks to clarify the legal standard to be applied to professional opinion in order to negate the reliance on particular opinions.¹⁸ There is lack of information as to the procedure to follow and the forum to lodge a medical negligence complaint immediately if it happens within the health facilities.

¹⁷ Prof.Justin 2014

¹⁸ General Principles of Medical Negligence and Background of the Civil Liability

The governing and monitoring medical bodies exist however their feasibility is lacking as opposed to the traditional legal avenue of reporting to police authority or seeking justice through courts of law¹⁹. This brings in some questions such as; are services users' aware of their rights? What can be done to mitigate medical negligence and malpractice in Rwanda?

This study looked at these issues to establish where the problem lies exactly. The study has critically analyzed the current status of medical negligence, the challenges favoring medical malpractices, the level of awareness among medical services users, and proposed the practical mitigation measures.

0.4. Research questions

This research has responded to following question

- i. What is the status and extent of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda?
- ii. Are medical services users' aware about their rights?
- iii. Which are the factors contributing to medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda?
- iv. What are the practical mitigation measures?

0.5. Research Hypotheses

- i. The current status and extent of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda is critical.
- ii. Medical services users are not aware about their rights.
- iii. Many factors contribute to medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda.
- iv. There are practical mitigation measures addressing the medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda.

¹⁹ Herman & Elizabeth, 2014

0.6. Research Objectives

This research intended to achieve these following general and specific objectives.

0.6.1. General Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study was the assessment of the status of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda.

0.6.2. Specific objectives

- i. To assess the current status and extent of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda;
- ii. To evaluate the medical services users' awareness about their rights
- iii. To identify the factors contributing to medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda;
- iv. To propose practical mitigation measures for medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda.

0.7. Significance of the study

Medical negligence has far reaching implications on health care facilities, government and the patient. Medical negligence increases the cost of medical care, the cost spent on compensations by government and health care facilities, and generally erodes patient confidence in the health sector. The charter of patients from the Ministry of Health provides that all Rwandans, regardless of gender, sexual orientation, age, religion, cultural belief or handicap, are equally entitled to receive health services to promote and maintain good health. Therefore, conducting this study and formulating relevant policy and legislative proposals will contribute to the achievement of this objective. The study sought to explore solutions that would address these challenges and safeguard patients' rights.

0.7. Subdivision of the study

This study consists in four parts. The first part comprised the general introduction; the second part (chapter 1) in conceptual and theoretical framework including cases review and legal framework, the third part (chapter 2) comprised the results analysis whereas the fourth and last part comprises the conclusion and recommendations.

0.8. Conclusion of the general introduction

The general introduction has consisted in exploring the background of the study comprising the historic and conceptual perspective of medical negligence and malpractice. The scope of the study has limited it in time and space. The increase of medical malpractice cases in the recent past has been highlighted in the problem statement and four research questions along with corresponding research questions, hypotheses and objectives have been formulated. The study is of high significance since it explores the solutions that would address the challenges upraised in the problem statement. Finally, the study has been subdivided in four parts comprising the general introduction, theoretical and conceptual framework, used methodology, analysis of findings and the general conclusion and recommendations.

CHAPTER 1: CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1.1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Medical malpractice claims arise when a healthcare professional fails to provide a patient the standard quality of care, thus resulting in an injury or harm to the patient. Medical malpractice can take place in any and every healthcare facility by any type of medical personnel, including internists, surgeons, nurses, and support staff⁴⁵. This section explores different concepts related to medical negligence and malpractice.

1.1.1. Medical Negligence and malpractice

Medical negligence also known as medical malpractice is improper, unskilled, or negligent treatment of a patient by a physician, dentist, nurse, pharmacist, or other health care professional. Medical malpractice occurs when a health-care provider strays from the recognized “standard of care” in the treatment of a patient²⁰. The “*standard of care*” is defined as what a reasonably prudent medical provider would or would not have done under the same or similar circumstances²⁰.

Mistakes or Negligence in medical profession may lead to minor injuries or some serious kinds of injuries and sometimes these kinds of mistakes may even cause death. Since no man is perfect in this world, it is evident that a person who is skilled and has knowledge over a particular subject can also commit mistakes during his practice. Too err is human but to replicate the same mistake due to one’s carelessness is negligence. The fundamental reason behind medical error or medical negligence is the carelessness of the said doctors or medical professionals it can be observed in various cases where reasonable care is not taken during the diagnosis, during operations, sometimes while injecting anesthesia.

There are distinct definitions for negligence. It is the omission to do something which a reasonable man, guided by those considerations which ordinarily regulate the conduct of human affairs, would do or doing something which a prudent and reasonable man would not do. It must be determined in all cases by reference to the situation and knowledge of the parties and all the attendant circumstances. Conduct which is below the standard behavior established generally for protection of others against unreasonable risk of harm is negligence. As per Winfield, “Negligence as a tort is the breach of a legal duty to the care which results in damage, undesired by the defendant, to the plaintiff.”

Negligence doesn’t arise just because of a wrongful conduct by a person; it is essential that that misconduct has caused a foreseeable harm to the other. If there’s no harm, there’s no negligence. In *King v. Phillips* it was observed that the question of negligence arises only when there is a direct harm to the plaintiff by the misconduct and the harm should be foreseeable. Damage is an important ingredient to bring negligence under tort.

²⁰ The Law Dictionary

1.1.1.1. Negligence as a Tort

A tort is a residuary civil wrong. Duties in tort are fixed by the law and such duties are owed in rem or to the people at large generally. Such wrongs can be remedied by filing for unliquidated damages. There may also be cases where concurrent liability may exist under tort and contract. For instance, if there is a contract existing between a patient and a doctor, then the doctor, for his negligence, will be liable under contract²¹.

1.1.1.2. Negligence as a Crime

Negligence as a crime has a different yardstick. Negligence under tort is determined on the extent of the loss caused whereas negligence under criminal law is dependent on the degree or amount of negligence. Courts have repeatedly held that the burden of proving criminal negligence rests heavily on the person claiming it. Criminal law requires a guilty mind. If there is a guilty mind, a practitioner will be liable in any case. But if, under the criminal law, rashness and recklessness amount to crime, then also a very high degree of rashness would be required to prove charges of criminal negligence against a medical practitioner. In other words, the element of criminality is introduced not only by a guilty mind, but by the practitioner having run the risk of doing something with recklessness and indifference to the consequences. It should be added that this negligence or rashness or must be 'gross' in nature²¹.

1.1.2. Medical Malpractice Liability

Medical malpractice liability is a relatively new but rapid growing area of law since the twentieth century²². Medical malpractice liability refers to which person or parties should be held legally responsible for the patient's injuries. This is usually the party that breached their duty of care, and was the actual cause of the patient's injuries. But in some cases, it can be difficult to tell exactly who the liable parties are. For instance, medical malpractice liability can often involve more than one party.

²¹ Aakarsh Shah, RNPI law school, 2017

²² Man H. (2013)

It is possible for medical malpractice liability may be split between both a doctor and nurse whose negligence caused the injury. For instance, if wrong instructions were given, or if one professional failed to correct the other, there may be a chance that both parties can be held liable. A hospital organization can also sometimes be held liable for malpractice, especially in cases where the overall policy or quality of care of the hospital is substandard²³.

1.1.3. Elements of medical negligence and malpractice

Once a lawsuit is filed, the patient alleging medical malpractice must generally prove four elements or legal requirements to make out a successful claim of medical malpractice. These elements include: (1) the existence of a legal duty on the part of the doctor to provide care or treatment to the patient; (2) a breach of this duty by a failure of the treating doctor to adhere to the standards of the profession; (3) a causal relationship between such breach of duty and injury to the patient; and (4) the existence of damages that flow from the injury such that the legal system can provide redress²⁴. This section provides details on these elements.

1.1.3.1. Existence of a legal duty

The first element is that a legal duty existed toward the patient; this duty comes into play whenever a professional relationship is established between the patient and health care provider. The general idea of a legal duty is that in civilized society, each person owes a duty of reasonable care to others. Extending this concept to the professional setting, where a doctor provides service to a patient, the doctor is said to owe a duty of reasonable professional care to the patient. In practical terms, this is the easiest element for the patient to establish, since such a duty is essentially assumed whenever a physician undertakes the care of a patient. A duty does not exist where no relationship is established between the doctor and patient; but when a relationship is established, such as covering patients for a colleague, covering a clinic where indigent patients are treated, or providing emergency services to an accident victim by the roadside, a duty of reasonable care follows²⁴.

²³ Legal Match, 2018

²⁴ B. S. Bal, MD, MBA, (2008).

In some situations, for policy reasons related to promoting medical care for indigent patients, or encouraging intervention by medical bystanders in case of an accident, the law may limit the liability of the treating physician, even though a reasonable duty of care was established. An exception to the duty of care is when the physician sees the patient as a nonprofessional, such as outside the hospital or clinic, or in some social setting. In such cases, no doctor relationship is established, and there is no duty of reasonable medical care owed.

1.1.3.2. Breach of legal duty

To show that a breach of professional duty occurred, the patient must invoke the concept of standard of care. While the precise definition of “standard of care” can differ among jurisdictions and the concept can prove elusive in its application, the standard of care generally refers to that care which a reasonable, similarly situated professional would have provided to the patient. To establish breach of a standard of professional care, expert witness testimony becomes essential since a jury of laypersons cannot understand the nuances of medical care²⁴.

Some breaches of the standard of care are so egregious that expert testimony is not needed; thus an operation on the wrong limb is an obvious breach of duty that speaks for itself. This concept is captured in the legal term called *res ipsa loquitur* (Latin for “the thing itself speaks” but more often translated as “the thing speaks for itself”); in such cases, the legal proceeding is abbreviated and the jury can proceed to determining damages since the breach of duty is plainly obvious. A breach of the standard of care in itself, aside from being a potential quality of care concern for the medical practitioner or institution, is legally meaningless unless it causes an injury to the patient²⁶.

1.1.3.3. Causal connection between the breach and injury

After it is established that a doctor had a duty and was negligent in performing that duty, the patient’s attorney must be able to demonstrate that the doctor’s conduct caused injury or harm. Generally, in a malpractice case, the causal connection is made by showing that the patient’s health situation worsened because of the doctor’s negligence and that the worsened condition would not have occurred in the absence of the doctor’s negligence. Sometimes, a doctor’s error can result in complications or create new health issues that require additional treatment.

If a doctor makes a mistake setting a child's broken arm, and as a result, the fracture does not heal properly, additional surgery and corrective treatments are necessary. Had the doctor not made the mistake, the fracture would have healed properly, and the additional treatment would not have been necessary, so the necessary causal connection exists²⁵. In other situations, such as when a doctor's negligence occurs during the diagnostic phase of treatment, the negligence may mean that necessary treatment was not received in a timely manner. For example, if a doctor's error results in a failure to diagnose cancer, the patient can be harmed by the delay in treatment on account of worsening of the condition and a change in the feasibility of specific treatment options.

In some cases, the doctor's failure may even mean the difference between life and death for the patient. In contrast, if a doctor makes an error, but the patient is not injured, there is not a valid malpractice claim. In the earlier example, if the doctor used the wrong procedure to set the child's broken arm, but the arm healed properly anyhow, the child was not injured. In that situation, a valid claim for malpractice would not exist²⁵.

1.1.3.4. Measurable harm from the injury

The fourth and final element of medical malpractice lawsuits is called damages. A medical malpractice claim generally concludes with a calculation of damages. Since monetary damages are easy to calculate and administer, courts hearing medical malpractice cases will determine money damages to compensate the injured patient. Punitive damages are very rare in medical malpractice cases, and are reserved by courts for especially egregious conduct that society has a particular interest in deterring. Absent a showing of damages, a plaintiff cannot maintain a cause of action for medical negligence²⁵.

In the example of the child with a broken arm, if the fracture did not heal properly because of the doctor's error in setting it, the child would need additional treatment to repair the arm. Damages would include the cost of the additional medical care, and the requirement for measurable injuries is met²⁵. But if the fracture went on to uneventful healing despite the wrong treatment and the patient pleaded injury from this treatment but with no showing of actual damages, there would be nothing for the court to award²⁴.

²⁵ Thomas Robenalt, 2017

1.1.4. Tort law and medical malpractice

Medical malpractice, or negligence law, is just one subset of the legal behemoth that is tort law. A tort is generally defined as a civil wrong which causes an injury, for which a victim may seek damages, typically in the form of money damages, against the alleged wrongdoer. Tort law is that body of law that serves as the vehicle by which tort liability can be sought in a court of law against such wrongdoers and generally serves to award damages to a victim sufficient to restore him to the position he would have been in, had the tortious conduct not occurred²⁶.

Tort law typically governs three legal theories of a lawsuit: negligence, strict liability, and intentional torts. The element of damages in tort law is of major significance and is integral to understanding the overall concept of tort reform, mainly because the “runaway juries” have been the subject of great media attention and inspection. In tort law compensatory money damages can be sought by a victim for both economic and noneconomic losses. Economic damages seek to compensate an individual for quantifiable economic losses, such as lost income and medical bills, while noneconomic damages are more speculative and seek to compensate an individual for noneconomic losses, such as mental distress and pain and suffering²⁶.

In certain rare scenarios, generally involving egregiously reckless conduct or behavior, a victim may also seek punitive damages against a wrongdoer. A significant medical malpractice crisis in the United States occurred in the 1970s and 1980s. During this time period, there was a rapid rise in the number of medical malpractice claims filed, as well as the size of awards made in medical malpractice actions. It has been estimated by the American Medical Association that in 1975 as many as 14,000 malpractice suits were filed against physicians. The average jury award in these suits was \$171,000²⁶.

The influx of medical malpractice claims and their subsequent jury awards created a chain reaction that had a far reaching effect. Many private insurance companies began withdrawing from providing insurance coverage, and the insurers that remained responded by raising malpractice premiums. In 1975, it was documented that malpractice premiums had increased from anywhere from 100% to 750%²⁶.

²⁶ David M. O., Meagan A. L., Stephanie P. O. & Adrienne D. D., 2011

The sudden increase in insurance premiums, coupled with the loss of many private insurance companies from the market, resulted in some physicians leaving particular practice areas, or retiring from the practice of medicine altogether. It was the culmination of these factors that sparked a call for policy change at both the state and federal levels, and with that, modern medical malpractice tort reform was born²⁶.

1.1.5. Hippocratic Oath

The Hippocratic Oath is an oath taken by doctors swearing to practice medicine ethically. It is widely believed to have been written by Hippocrates, the father of western medicine, in Ionic Greek late 5th century BC. Hippocratic Oath hastens the moral conduct of physicians, assuming the respect for all human life, even the unborn. Medical profession is one of the oldest professions of the world and is the most humanitarian one. Inherent in the concept of any profession is a code of conduct, containing the basic ethics that underline the moral values that govern professional practice and is aimed at upholding its dignity. Medical Ethics underpins the values at the heart of the practitioner-client relationship. Medical negligence and malpractices by doctors are grey areas in health care where legal issues arise³.

The oath is the earliest expression of medical ethics in the Western world, establishing several principles of medical ethics which remain of paramount significance today. These include the principles of medical confidentiality and non-maleficence. As the seminal articulation of certain principles that continue to guide and inform medical practice, the ancient text is of more than historic and symbolic value. Swearing a modified form of the oath remains a rite of passage for medical graduates in many countries, and is a requirement enshrined in legal statutes of various jurisdictions, such that violations of the oath may carry criminal or other liability beyond the oath's symbolic nature.

The Hippocratic Oath has been eclipsed as a document of professional ethics by more extensive, regularly updated ethical codes issued by national medical associations, such as the AMA Code of Medical Ethics (first adopted in 1847), and the British General Medical Council's Good Medical Practice. These documents provide a comprehensive overview of the obligations and professional behavior of a doctor to their patients and wider society.

Doctors who violate these codes may be subjected to disciplinary proceedings, including the loss of their license to practice medicine. There is no direct punishment for breaking the Hippocratic Oath, although an arguable equivalent in modern times is medical malpractice which carries a wide range of punishments, from legal action to civil penalties²⁷.

1.2. Theoretical framework

Rwandan jurisdictions struggle to maintain a fair and efficient system for adjudicating malpractice complaints-one that denies meritless claims and compensates claims with merit while holding physicians accountable, deterring negligence, uncovering mistakes, and encouraging quality care. To these ends and in accordance to research objectives, this section explores different literatures related to medical malpractice.

²⁷ Groner M.D., Johnathan (2008).

Figure 2: Theoretical framework

1.2.1. General background of medical negligence and malpractice

We live in a litigious society, and the medical community is now feeling the impact of this reality. There are occasions when patients are harmed as a consequence of their treatment or absence of treatment. It is well known that beneficial activities can lead to costly outcomes ('harm', 'injury'), e.g. on the road or in the operating theatre. Such costly outcomes can be reduced if the beneficial activities themselves are cut down, or if those involved take care to avoid them. However, to the extent that care is also costly, people may need to be given incentives to provide it. One natural incentive is to make the person causing the harm liable for the costs involved, if s/he fails to supply care beyond a sufficient threshold (i.e. behaves 'negligently'). This potential attribution of fault provides a deterrent against insufficient care levels³⁰.

In theory, the appropriate level of care should maximize the net gains to society from the beneficial activities involved: this means that the marginal social benefit from an extra unit of care should equal its marginal social cost. In other words, the extra benefit to society (in terms of reduction in injury rates and their associated costs) from an extra unit of care should just equal the extra resource cost to society of the extra unit of care itself. It should be understood that the notions of benefit and cost here are broader than simple monetary amounts.

In a world where the standard of care is known to everyone, and observable (to individuals and courts), it is straightforward to show that negligence liability would produce socially optimal levels of care (i.e. deterrence). However, common sense and the observation that many people buy liability insurance, tell us that these conditions are strict and that, in practice, overwhelming information problems prevent such a result. For example, courts cannot determine precisely what care a clinician has taken, while it is often the case that opinions differ as to what constitutes an appropriate standard of care. This can have numerous implications for the successful operation of a negligence system. Particularly important here is that if the care threshold and courts' abilities to apply it are unpredictable, parties worried about mistakenly being found liable may over-invest in care. In the medical context, this is what is known as 'defensive medicine'²⁸

²⁸ Paul, F. et al. (2002)

Negligence-based liability for medical malpractice appears to involve higher administrative costs than alternative means of providing compensation. Therefore, a necessary condition for the adoption of negligence based compensation is that it provides net deterrence benefits. One, apparent, way to overcome this problem is to move to a system of ‘strict liability’, where proof of causation is sufficient to trigger compensation from the party whose actions led to the harm. Because this payment is made regardless of the injurer’s level of care, it overcomes problems associated with unpredictable care thresholds. Also, to the extent that the injurer faces the costs of his/her actions, it can be shown to provide optimal incentives for care (i.e. deterrence). Once more, however, real-world imperfections make this unlikely in practice²⁹

Evidence from the UK lends tentative support to the view that hospitals with a higher share of tort liability are more likely to take action to reduce the frequency and stock of claims. Consequently, current moves to reduce malpractice cases levels to zero in the UK may have adverse consequences in terms of a higher number of claims. Efforts to replace the incentives provided by excess levels through the adoption of risk management discounts do not appear to have a strong effect. Any move to reform the current tort system by changing the basis of liability in the UK should make sure that incentives are not diluted in the search for administrative efficiency and improved access to compensation³⁰.

In Rwanda, Between 30 and 40 medical practitioners are reprimanded annually over varying cases of professional malpractices, according to the Rwanda Medical and Dental Council. However, people hear of few medical-related cases in Rwandan courts. A number of them are managed by the medical council and penalties meted out include deregistration, and suspension for varying periods. The main challenge faced while adjudicating cases of medical malpractice in Rwanda is establishing the level of responsibility and the level at which the medical care provided to a patient was below minimum required standards³¹.

²⁹ Cummins et al. (2001)

³⁰ Paul, F. et al. (2002)

³¹ The new times, August 30, 2013

1.2.2. Extent of current medical malpractice situation

In recent years, the world has seen a sharp increase in medical malpractice litigation. A number of factors have contributed to this increase and doctors as well as other healthcare providers have been profoundly affected thereby. It's estimated that 440,000 people are killed by medical errors every year, making it the third leading cause of death in the world, after heart disease and cancer. In other words, medical malpractice is responsible for 1,200 fatalities a day³². It seems as though the proliferation of claims for the adverse consequences of medical intervention, which has been a rising global trend, has eventually reached all countries. Not only has there been an increase in the frequency of claims, but the amounts that have been awarded have also risen significantly.

The lack of information on the extent of medical malpractice is problematic, the causes and prevalence of medical errors would be much easier to assess and address if the data was readily available. Media and other reports do however provide a general idea of the current medical malpractice situation³³. According to a 2011 report by Towers Watson, since 1975, when medical malpractice insurance data were first separated out from other types of liability in USA, medical malpractice cost increases have outpaced other tort areas, rising at an average of 10.0 percent a year, compared with 7.5 percent for all other tort costs. However, growth in medical malpractice costs since 2005 have averaged less than 0.5 percent annually. Regardless of whether a case is won or lost, going to court is expensive³⁴.

A study reported in the *New England Journal of Medicine* (August 2011) found that 7.4 percent of all physicians could expect a medical malpractice claim to be filed against them in any given year but only 1.6 percent of physicians would be subject to a claim that would lead to a payment. This translated into 78 percent of all claims resulting in no payment to the claimant. The researchers studied claims received by one major medical malpractice insurer, from 1991 through 2005 with a nationwide client base³⁴.

³² Davis L. L., 2019

³³ Oosthuizen & Carstens, May 2015

³⁴ Insurance Information Institute, Inc, 2012

In Rwanda, despite the act containing quite elaborate provisions on disciplinary measures, cases of medical malpractice have been on the increase in the recent past. Fifty-three medical litigation cases were identified in Rwanda from 2008 to 2013³⁵. In essence there are many silent potential cases of medical malpractice which have not been addressed mainly because the victims either do not have confidence in the professional regulatory bodies or are scared of the procedures and complexities associated with the court process. Although there is little empirical information available on the incidence of medical malpractice and the subsequent claims, the available information suggests that the extent of the situation is dire³⁵.

Calls for reform are justified, but will only be effective if the causes of malpractice and the related claims are properly identified and understood. Ideally, one would want to prevent claims and costs by reducing malpractice. For this to happen the quality of care provided must improve and patient safety should be promoted. Research on how the liability and compensation system could be aligned with such an objective, whilst being more effective at preventing malpractice, is required³³.

1.2.3. Public awareness on medical malpractice

Stakeholders in the medical profession have indicated that the proliferation of complaints and litigation is not due to a decline in standards and care, but rather due to the fact that patients are more aware of their rights. This is a development that should be welcomed, as patients who have legitimate claims must be compensated³³. People are more educated now than before. They are aware of their rights.

In India for example, the public can procure their rights through Consumer protection act. 69% of them knew the term consumer protection act. Consumer protection act came out in 1986 which means any fault, imperfection, shortcoming, or inadequacy in the quality, nature, or manner of performance that is required to be maintained by or under any law for being in force at that given time³⁶.

³⁵ Ncayiyana, 2004

³⁶ Uma et al., 2020

In Kenya for example, and especially following the enactment of a new constitution, which gives all Kenyans the right to access quality care and free access to emergency services, there has been an unprecedented increase in media coverage of medical malpractice complaints from the public, ranging from clinical care processes gone wrong to complaints of outright unethical practices and behaviors.

The media coverage is merely a response to an increased public awareness and the demand for information on how the health system is performing, and an interest in knowing what those in authority are doing to ensure that health services are provided in a safe and humane manner. As a result, the Kenya Medical Practitioners and Dentists Board (KMPDB) and other regulators have had to constantly engage the media to respond to complaints and explain what it is doing to dispense justice and improve the situation³⁷.

In 2013, the government, in consultation with its health sector partners, established the law No. 49/2012, which instituted medical professional liability insurance. This law elaborates medical service users' rights and the responsibilities of health service providers. Additionally, it identifies compensation benefits for health care users who, due to medical service(s) that was provided to them, were rendered incapable of leading the life they used to live prior to receiving care. Unfortunately, most service users lack knowledge of their legal rights, which hinders improvement of service quality. This barrier to delivering quality services has been noted by several organizations, including the government of Rwanda³⁸.

Awareness towards medical negligence is increasing day by day among patients. Recent court rulings have also been in favor of the complainants where there is proven case of negligence which has encouraged others to take up their grievances. Medical personnel must be aware in their practice that patients are becoming more aware of their rights. The public becomes unforgiving when there is perceived harm to patients as a result of medical negligence. Medical professionals all have to be litigious conscious and therefore have a basic knowledge on avoidance of malpractice and litigations³³.

³⁷ Njeri et al. 2016

³⁸ Rwandan law on medical liability insurance (2013).

1.2.4. Factors contributing to medical negligence and malpractice

In the recent past, claims of medical Negligence/malpractice by medical practitioners have been on the increase with most of the victims blaming the procedural inadequacies in the disciplinary process. Scarcity of physicians, poor training, lack of adherence to policies, other health priorities, regulatory deficits and weak civil societies are ones of the most contributing³⁹ and this section provides details on each of them.

1.2.4.1. Scarcity of Physicians

The health sector is currently in a crisis in respect of human resources and it has been described as the most pressing issue affecting healthcare globally. The World Health Organization (WHO) has estimated that there is a global shortage of approximately 4.3 million nurses, doctors, midwives, and other members of the multidisciplinary healthcare professionals. The global shortage threatens the sustainability and quality of health systems worldwide. The increased workload demand on healthcare worker may also account for a poor standard of medical care delivered, as they are prone to make mistakes, contributing to the negligence claims³⁹.

In a study conducted at a Malawian hospital, it was found that professional standards in obstetric care cannot be met due to a lack of skilled medical staff, forcing shortcuts in the medical care provided. The challenges of having a shortage of medical staff and too many patients were further exacerbated by the lack of skills needed to treat obstetric complications, mainly due to the locum doctors who do not have the adequate expertise to address an emergency⁴⁰.

A study conducted within the intensive care units in South Africa has researched the nurse managers' views on staffing and found that the number of personnel members is not sufficient in comparison to the number of patients within the specialized area. This shortage in skilled staff members has a great effect on the quality of nursing care provided within the intensive care unit. Specialized care is being provided by staff members who are neither trained nor educated to do so.

³⁹ Amy W. 2018.

⁴⁰ Bradley et al., 2015

One participant expressed that due to the shortage of skilled intensive care registered nursing practitioners, the health organization relies on the skills of enrolled nurses to care for patients being ventilated⁴¹. In Frere Hospital in East London, the care of patients is at risk due to the shortage of nurses in the Intensive care unit. There should be a ratio of one intensive care nurse to one patient, due to the specialized needs the patient requires. Nevertheless, due to staff shortages within the hospital, the nursing staffs are compelled to care for more than one patient³⁹

1.2.4.2. Poor Training

Proper training is important for every employee of a medical facility, especially for employees who directly interact with and care for patients. Without proper training, healthcare professionals may not properly perform tasks, putting patients at risk of injury or death. It's also important to keep in mind that medical knowledge and treatments are always evolving, therefore keeping healthcare professionals up to date through ongoing training is essential for the wellbeing of patients. Without proper training or ongoing education, employees may lack sufficient knowledge and fall below the standard of care⁴².

There are many ways in which medical malpractice may occur as a result of substandard training. Even errors in small, daily tasks, like hand washing, can lead to patient injury. Even tasks that seem like common sense must be included in training and enforced through hospital or the healthcare facility's protocol. Unfortunately, when training is lacking it can lead to substandard care, which ultimately may harm the patient.

⁴¹ Matlakala et al., 2016

⁴² Younker H.M., 2019

1.2.4.3. Lack of adherence to policies

A study conducted in two district hospitals in Rwanda has identified lack of adherence to standards and guidelines for postpartum care management factors influencing the job performance of midwives and nurses in postpartum units. The high rates of postpartum complications, as well as the patients' complaints regarding the quality of nursing care within the maternity unit were reflections of the lack of adherence to policies that provide the necessary procedures to prevent life-threatening complications after birth.⁴³

1.2.4.4. Other Health Priorities

Another factor that contributes to malpractice is that medical practitioners are often beset by other health policy priorities, which can relegate patients' rights to a secondary or even tertiary concern⁴⁴. HIV/AIDS, malaria, Covid19, swine flu, and other infectious diseases plague countries like India, China, and many African nations. For example, in India, "someone dies every minute from tuberculosis." These countries may rightly dedicate more time and attention to addressing public health crises than things like medical negligence⁴⁴.

1.2.4.5. Regulatory Deficits

Developing countries largely lack the regulatory capacity to set and enforce standards on health care providers. In contrast, developed countries, like the United States, can rely on overlapping layers of laws and regulations to encourage physicians, hospitals, and other providers to meet at least some minimum standards." But even the larger, wealthier developing countries, like India and China, lack an overall framework for regulating their health sectors. For example, in theory, India can rely on the Medical Council of India, various Departments of Health, the Indian Medical Association, and other regulatory or quasi-regulatory bodies to oversee practitioners. But self-regulation by professional medical societies is weak and ineffectual. Instead of sanctioning recalcitrant members, medical societies are more likely to ignore and minimize their behavior⁴⁴.

⁴³ Uwaliraye et al., 2013.

⁴⁴ Nathan C., 2011

Many developing countries focus on regulating licensing and entry into the medical professions, rather than reviewing medical professionals' performance retrospectively." As a result, medical professionals can escape meaningful regulation in these jurisdictions. Aside from regulating medical professionals, developing countries often lack effective hospital regulation" and consumer protection regimes. Some of the regulatory deficits in developing countries may be attributable to timing-the health sectors in these countries have grown considerably over the last few decades without a corresponding growth in their regulating capacity. Ultimately, legal redress is particularly important in developing countries precisely because of their weak regulatory oversight of the health industry and professions⁴⁴.

1.2.4.6. Weak Civil Societies

If a country cannot regulate its health practitioners or if its efforts are not legitimate, institutionalized, and above all enforced, then the public might fall back on civil society and civil institutions for support. Unfortunately, many developing countries lack strong civil societies to account for their regulatory deficits. The media can be crucial at uncovering and raising public awareness of medical negligence, and fortunately, some developing countries, such as Rwanda, have a relatively strong media. But not all developing countries can count on their media in such a manner. In addition, the media often relies on court decisions and other formal adjudications to inform them of medical malpractice. Accordingly, such circumstances amplify the need for patients in developing countries to have a genuine avenue for redressing their medical complaints⁴⁴.

1.2.4.7. Patients as Regulatory Sentinels

Rounding out this picture, patients in developing countries are less equipped than patients in the developed world to act as regulatory sentinels, uncovering and reporting medical negligence. Patients in these countries are less able to access, process, and understand information about the medical care they receive. For example, many patients in the developing world who rely on informal practitioners are frequently unaware that they are not professionally trained. The information asymmetries between patients and providers can be particularly severe in developing countries, which further distorts the power dynamic between them.

Patients in poverty are even less likely to have the requisite literacy, education, and financial resources to challenge their doctors. Some believe that medical professionals unethically exploit these imbalances. If patients cannot appraise the quality or value of the care they receive, then they are much less likely to serve as early sentinels. Developing countries thus lack a key layer of - patient surveillance on practitioners. Compounding matters, residents of developing countries may be reluctant to sue because they are either unaware of their legal rights, feel powerless to invoke their legal rights against medical professionals or institutions, or have other cultural aversions to litigation⁴⁴.

1.2.5. The Effects of Medical Malpractice

Every year, medical malpractice is a serious problem for thousands of people across the world. Medical malpractice can take place in any and every healthcare facility by any type of medical personnel, including internists, surgeons, nurses, and support staff. Moreover, an article published in the Journal of the American Medical Association noted that every year in the United States almost 12,000 patient deaths occur due to unnecessary surgery, 7,000 deaths were caused by medication errors in hospitals, and 20,000 deaths resulted from other errors in hospitals. The Journal of the American Association for Justice stated that a decade ago as many as 98,000 people died every year from preventable medical errors, costing the nation an estimated \$29 billion dollars⁴⁵.

Medical malpractice can negatively affect all aspects of an injured patient's life, from physical and emotional damages to serious financial hardships. Results such as loss of work, permanent disability, loss of quality of life, and loss of future wages are a few examples of the possible negative impacts. Furthermore, when death is the result of medical negligence, "the surviving dependents or beneficiaries may be entitled to monetary damages in order to help pay for medical costs and other expenses incurred by the family of the victim. Medical malpractice affects both patients and physicians severely. Thus, it is crucial to examine the effects of medical malpractice claims against physicians. This article aims at examining the impact that medical malpractice claims have on physicians and quality of care⁴⁵.

⁴⁵ Jonathan, T., 2010.

1.2.5.1. The effect of medical malpractice on physicians

Legal action can result in other costs, including mental distress, lost time from work, and a damaged reputation. Medical malpractice lawsuits can impose more than just a financial burden upon physicians. There is significant research showing that coping with a medical malpractice suit can weigh heavily on a physician. No one wishes an ill outcome on a patient, and physicians are especially challenged when there is an unexpected outcome, such as an unanticipated death, followed by a charge of malpractice. In this situation, a physician may feel overwhelmed and out of control. Often physicians take the accusation of malpractice personally, and some are prone to symptoms of depression, adjustment disorder, the onset of a physical illness, alcoholism, or drug misuse⁴⁶

1.2.5.2. The effects of malpractice on patients

The effects of malpractice on patients, whether or not they are actually involved in a legal suit, can be substantial. News or rumors of malpractice for a medical practice or hospital can be a turnoff for potential patients, making them reluctant to seek help. Concerns regarding negligence can make patients nervous and impede a trustworthy and open interaction; the cornerstone of doctor-patient relationships. Malpractice may even affect the cost of healthcare. Physicians and other healthcare providers have long argued that malpractice claims are the leading cause of escalating healthcare costs. The worry is that as malpractice legal suits become more commonplace, and claimants receive settlements for millions of dollars, patients will have to swallow some of these costs through higher insurance premiums and doctor's fees⁴⁷.

Malpractice insurance premiums for doctors can also affect patients. The premiums can vary drastically by state and by medical specialty. Rising premiums may cause doctors to move to states with more manageable costs, which in turn will greatly influence patient access to the best doctors. Access to healthcare may grow increasingly limited in areas where premiums are especially high. Another concern for patients arises from doctors practicing "defensive medicine," a euphemism for the ordering of additional tests and procedures that are not strictly necessary but provide protection against claims of negligence and malpractice charges⁴⁷.

⁴⁶ Sara C. C, 2001.

⁴⁷ Texas A&M University, 2016

1.2.6. Solutions to medical malpractice

There are potential solutions to minimize the effects of medical malpractice lawsuits. In the current malpractice insurance crisis, physicians have focused their advocacy and energy primarily on rapidly increasing liability premiums; problems in access to care; and demands for legal reform, especially caps on damages. An even more important focus, however, is prevention of injury and improvement of patient safety. Physicians largely control patient care and can play a critical role in systematically reducing injury. Reforms should go beyond liability issues; they should also harness and enhance physicians' ability to act. More visible efforts by physicians to reduce harm, better communication with patients and others, and true evidence of improved patient safety should reduce patient anger and litigiousness. Individually and collectively, physicians can and should ensure that "doing no harm" comes first in the malpractice debate⁴⁸.

The solutions to the problems of medical malpractice and malpractice insurance coverage are primarily in the hands of state legislatures. Legislation enacted has been primarily palliative, to assure continued availability of professional liability insurance. Unfortunately, no limit can be placed on the costs of such coverage. Unfortunately, too, no long-term solution has been forthcoming. Any long-term solution must encompass methods of reducing injuries to patients and at the same time changing the system from defense of the physician to compensation of the patient. If such changes are not forthcoming, physicians will become uninsurable and the private practice of medicine as we now know it will disappear in this country⁴⁸.

1.3. Negligence cases review

Cases of medical negligence have increased sharply in the past few years, raising concern about the level of professionalism in the Rwandan medical sector. According to the Rwanda Medical and Dental Council, cases of medical malpractice doubled from 12 reported in 2014 to 27 in 2015 and 34 in 2016. This section examines some cases occurred in some Rwandan health facilities.

⁴⁸ Stephen C. S. & Randall R. B., (2014)

1.3.1. Rwanda Military Hospital, King Faisal, Fined Rwf100M for Mistakenly Cutting off Patient's Breast⁴⁹

The Gasabo intermediate court has fined King Faisal Hospital and Kanombe Military hospital for cutting off the breast of a patient after mistakenly diagnosing her with a level two cancer. The two national referral hospitals must pay the patient Rwf100 million (over US\$100,000) with immediate effect for what the court described as “medical negligence”. The verdict was delivered on Friday April 9, 2021 after an almost two-year legal battle.

The Military Hospital executed the operation following a medical report from King Faisal Hospital. In the court, the Military Hospital denied liability claiming the report from King Faisal Hospital was categorical that the patient had a level 2 breast cancer and that what doctors at the Military Hospital had to do was to cut it off. King Faisal Hospital defended itself saying it had all the necessary equipment to conduct an operation and there is no reason why it would have referred the patient to another hospital. Apparently, the two hospitals share doctors, some medical services and joint operations. The court ruled that both hospitals were medically negligent and they had to be fined.

The patient, a resident of Kayonza District, had sued for Rwf305 million (US\$300,000). The Military hospital will pay Rwf62 million and King Faisal Hospital will pay Rwf42 million. The remaining will cater for legal fees and court fees. It is reported that the doctor who diagnosed the patient with cancer, Dr. Lynette Kyokunda, moved to Zambia where she continued with her medical career.

1.3.2. Masaka Hospital medic suspended over negligence

The Ministry of Health suspended in October 2018 a medical doctor at Masaka Hospital in Kicukiro District, accusing him of neglecting patients, including a five-year-old child. The allegations, leveled against the Doctor, were made on Twitter by a user claiming that her five-year old niece who was admitted at the hospital lacked proper medical attention due to negligence on the part of the doctor who was on duty.

⁴⁹ Taarifa Rwanda. 2021

Another social media user commented on the same thread, saying that another patient had died of neglect around the same time. Director of Masaka Hospital admitted that the doctor in question could have done more to help the five-year-old girl who was later transferred to Kanombe Military Hospital⁵⁰.

1.3.3. Case No RCAA 00073/2018/CA, Nyirabatesi Laurence vs King Faisal Hospital

The Kigali court of appeal has fined King Faisal Hospital for injuries caused upon Nyirabatesi Laurence resulting from negligence during delivery in November 2003. The hospitals must pay the patient Rwf120 million with immediate effect for what the court described as “damages for medical negligence”. The verdict was delivered on Friday July 19, 2019 after an almost ten-year legal⁵¹.

1.3.4. King Faisal hospital losses appeal in negligence case

King Faisal hospital and its insurer SONARWA have lost a long judicial battle against a patient who was awarded Rwf50 million (\$58,500) in damages for medical negligence. The Supreme Court dismissed the appeal by the hospital and the insurer, saying it did not have jurisdiction to hear the matter. “In both the intermediate Court and High Court, King Faisal Hospital lost the case because the court imputed the negligence to the hospital and according to the law, a case lost twice on the same grounds cannot be appealed against in the Supreme Court. This case started in the intermediate court in 2015 and was appealed in the high court. However, the high court confirmed the decision of the intermediate court⁵².

1.4. Legal framework for medical negligence and malpractice in Rwanda

Medical practice usually involves different activities which if not professionally handled, may give rise to liabilities on the part of the medical practitioner. These liabilities may arise in tortious claims and in some other cases, may go beyond the realm of civil liabilities to criminal liabilities. This review focuses different laws governing medical negligence and malpractice in Rwanda.

⁵⁰ Dushimimana, 2018

⁵¹ The judiciary of Rwanda, 2021

⁵² The East African Journal, February 2018

1.4.1. Constitution

Based on the Rwandan Constitution, Articles 41 and 45, which states that all citizens have rights and duties relating to health; the country has committed to ensure universal access to affordable promotive, preventive, curative, and rehabilitative health services of the highest attainable quality.

In this regard, Rwanda's Ministry of Health has revised its National Health Policy, based on Vision 2020 and EDPRS II. The health system consists of three levels of service provision: central, intermediary and peripheral. The central level includes the central directorates and programs of the Ministry of Health and the national referral hospitals. The largest health insurance program is the Community-Based Health Insurance Scheme (CBHI), estimated to cover 81.4% of the population, and highly subsidized by the Government of Rwanda⁵³

1.4.2. Penal code

The Penal Code in its article 2 defines the offence as an act prohibited or an omission which manifests itself as a breach of the public order and which the law sanctions by a punishment". Medical malpractice is a professional negligence by act or omission by a health care provider in which the treatment provided falls below the accepted standard of practice in the medical community and causes injury or death to the patient with most cases involving medical error. Standards and regulations for medical malpractice vary by country and jurisdictions within countries⁵⁴.

1.4.3. Law n°49/2012 of 22/01/2013 establishing medical professional liability insurance¹¹

This law was established by the ministry of health with the Rwanda medical and dental council for reconciliation and compensation for health risk. It is the law that protects the rights of patients and other service users. Those rights include;

- Right by human person to dignity and privacy
- Right of access to medical procedures
- Patient's right to safety

⁵³ Rwandan Constitution 2003 (rev. 2015)

⁵⁴ Prof. Justine W., (2014).

- Right to free choice of health professional
- Right to information
- Freedom of choice of a trusted person
- Right to consent
- Right to refuse treatment and withdraw consent
- Consent of minors and other incapable persons
- Right to consult and be given a copy of a patient's medical record
- Right to sue for compensation

This law also provides insurance against health risks, stating the compensation for health risks not covered under insurance policy. The patients/ victims are protected by this law in case of liability for pharmaceuticals and other devices having caused adverse events on the patient. This law also has provided the limitation of legal action which is 5 years from the date of occurrence of the risk or the date when the risk has been known¹¹.

1.5. Conclusion of conceptual and theoretical framework

Basing on the research objectives, the concepts and literatures related to medical negligence and malpractice were reviewed. The Medical Negligence and malpractice concepts were defined and the medical malpractice liability was explained. The elements of medical negligence and malpractice were listed and the concepts including Hippocratic Oath and tort law were reviewed.

The theoretical framework started with a general background of medical negligence and malpractice. With the purpose of achieving the research objective, the corresponding literatures were reviewed and these included the extent of current medical malpractice situation, the public awareness on medical malpractice, the factors contributing to medical negligence and malpractice, the effects of medical malpractice and the solutions to medical malpractice were explored. With the aim of enriching the review, four negligence cases were studied and the related legal framework was reviewed.

CHAPTER TWO: METHODOLOGY

2.1. Description of the area of study

2.1.1. Study Location

Musanze District is one of the six secondary cities and one of the 5 districts in the Northern Province of Rwanda. The total area of the district is 530 4 km², 60 km² occupied by the Volcanoes National Park and 28 km² accommodating Lake Ruhondo. Musanze City is about 94 km from Kigali on the major Kigali-Musanze-Rubavu-Goma road and it borders with Uganda and DR Congo in the North, Gakenke District in the South, Burera District in the East and Nyabihu District in the West⁵⁵.

Figure 3: Map of Musanze District⁵⁶

⁵⁵ Musanze DDS, 2018

⁵⁶ Habimana, 2015

2.1.2. Demography

The 4th Rwanda Population and Housing Census (PHC4) of 2012, has enumerated 368,267 inhabitants in Musanze District on a density of 694 Inhabitants/Km², where 47.4% are males and 52.6% are females; and 27.7% living in urban areas and 72.3% living in rural areas. Musanze population represents 3.5% of the total population of Rwanda. It represents 21.3 % of the Northern Province population (1,726,370 inhabitants). Muhoza is the highest populated (51,878) sector, whereas Nkotsi is the least (13,594). The recent data from Ubudehe Profiling carried out by LODA in February 2018 shows that there is a likely increase of habitants from 368,267 in 2012 to 406,479 in 2018⁵⁵.

2.1.3. Health

Musanze District has a total of 18 health facilities, made of: 16 health centers, 13 dispensaries and one referral hospital. According to DHS5, 457 Households that responded to the survey, 384 have at least one member covered by health insurance. The mean walking distance to a health center is one hour countrywide⁵⁵.

2.1.4. Promotion of Justice, Reconciliation, Law and Order

In the justice sector, respondents are most satisfied with the justice service provided by National police, local mediators and Judiciary with satisfaction ratings of 79%, 76% and 71% respectively. Scores are similar with prosecution, lawyers, and justice access bureaus that scored 67%, 60% and 56% respectively⁵⁵.

2.2. Research Methods

2.2.1. The study design

The study applied qualitative methods of data collection. This method has specifically been chosen to solicit views, perceptions and opinions. In this perspective, key informant interviews were used. Questionnaires were developed and distributed to technical persons dealing with medical issues and medical services users to generate technical information. In addition, related literature and related court cases were reviewed. Statistical information and surveys conducted by other relevant institutions and individuals on this study also used to supplement qualitative information collected.

2.2.1. Study population

A total of 50 respondents were targeted for this study and were all directly interviewed.

2.2.2. Sample selection

The study population comprised various stakeholders including medical practitioners, medical services users (health facilities customers), legal practitioners and law enforcement agencies such as RIB and Police operating in Musanze District.

Table 1: Sample determination

Category of respondents	Number
Medical Practitioners (Physicians, Nurses, Midwives and paramedical)	20
Health Facilities customers /Medical services users/Patients	20
Legal practice and enforcement (Lawyers, RIB and Police)	10
Total	50

Respondents for the qualitative data collection were purposively selected due to the uniqueness of this study. The use of purposive sampling aided the study in the collection of general views that have a bearing on the subject matter. In addition, the diversity nature of purposive sampling guaranteed representativeness of the study population.

2.2.3. Data collection

Both primary and secondary sources for the purpose of this study were reviewed and documented. Primary sources included study interviews, Rwandan laws and decided court cases. Basically, qualitative data were largely collected using individual interviews, key informant interviews and documentary review (literature review). Secondary sources included academic books by various authors, journal articles, dissertations and other materials relevant to the subject.

2.2.4. Data analysis

The data were coded, categorized and entered in computer to be analyzed using computer software packages MS Excel where frequency distribution and percentages were mostly used. The results were presented through text, Tables and Figures accompanied by according interpretations.

2.3. Conclusion of the research methodology

This study was carried out in Musanze District, Northern Province of Rwanda. The general objective was to assess the status of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District, Rwanda. Both primary and secondary data were collected. Questionnaire survey was used for primary data collection where purposive sampling was used. Secondary data were gathered from books, report, journals, magazines and internet. The collected data were analyzed by using Microsoft excel package.

CHAPTER 3: ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This Chapter presents the results of the study. The chapter starts with a description of socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the respondents. The descriptive analysis of the respondents' practices, perception and attitudes to towards medical negligence is then presented. These are the interviews responses, mainly based on the set of objectives and are in conformity with the research questions. Bar charts were used to present the findings and all results are presented in term of frequency (Percentages) along with tables indicating detailed information.

3.1. Gender status of respondents

Gender equality means equal rights and opportunities for women and men in laws and policies, and equal access to resources and services within families, communities and society at large. Thus, the gender representatively may influence the study outcome. The gender distribution status of respondents is presented in the Figure 2 below.

Figure 4: Gender status of respondents

The results in Figure 2 indicate that the number of males and female respondents is equal. The number is however slightly higher among males respondents in the category of medical practitioners and the while as the opposite situation is observed among patients category.

3.2 Age distribution

Age is a standard demographic component of research on social issues. The age distribution was included in this study to determine if there were any medical negligence experiences, perceptions or attitudes that are common to any particular group of age or whether the population as a whole shares the same experiences, perceptions and views. Three age groups had been identified among respondents and these are 20-30 years, 31-50 years and 51-Above. The situation is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 5: Respondents' age distribution

The situation in Figure 3 suggests that the majority of respondents (56%) are aged between 31 and 50 years. This coincides with the category of people in the prime working lives and this majority coupled with the 22% of the 51-above age group comprise the respondents experienced enough to provide expected information about medical negligence and malpractice.

Although you can suffer medical negligence at any time of your life, the age may influence the compensation process and thus, the behavior of medical practitioner. The UK's legal system for example severely limits the compensation available to older people. If the victim is already retired, he/she won't be able to claim for any loss of earnings, and this can significantly impact the amount of compensation he/she will receive. If you he/she still working, the losses will be calculated to the age at which he/she could have reasonably been expected to stop working, and that may not be far away⁵⁷.

3.3. Working experience of respondents

Experienced medical practitioners are expected to effectively fulfill their duties and avoid negligence while as experienced legal practitioners can effectively handle medical negligence cases. In addition, having worked in medical or legal field for a short or long time can impact a lot for the information provided by respondents. Thus, medical practitioners and law enforcement agents were asked about how long they have been working in their respective fields and the findings are presented in the figure 4.

⁵⁷ ENABLE LAW 2019

Figure 6: Respondents' work experience

As indicated by the findings in Figure 4, in the category of medical practitioners and law enforcement categories, a total of 56.6% of respondents have a working experience of more than 10 years. Only 16.6% of respondents have been working in their field for less than 5 years. These findings imply that the respondents are experienced enough to have been involved in medical negligence cases and thus, to provide expected information.

3.4. Occurrence of medical negligence and malpractice

With the purpose of evaluating the reliability of the information provided by respondents, this study managed to know if the respondent have ever been involved, witnessed or dealt with medical negligence and the findings are presented in the Figure 5.

Figure 7: Respondents' involvement, witnessing or dealing with medical negligence

As indicated by the findings in Figure 5, as many as 88% of all categories of respondents have been involved in a medical negligence case in one way or another whereas only 12% of respondents and mostly among patients said that they didn't. The implication is that the problem is critical and deserves to be searched and explored.

As reported by the *The New Times* (2013), between 30 and 40 medical practitioners are reprimanded annually over varying cases of professional malpractices, according to the Rwanda Medical and Dental Council. However, people hear of few medical-related cases in Rwandan courts. The main challenge faced while adjudicating cases of medical malpractice in Rwanda is establishing the level of responsibility and the level at which the medical care provided to a patient was below minimum required standards³¹

3.5. The action taken for medical negligence cases

As the majority of respondents (Section 4.4) admitted to have been involved in medical negligence and/medical malpractices case, the study sought to know what happens whenever a medical negligence or malpractice occurs. Patients and medical practitioners were then asked if the cases they have been involved in or have witnessed were taken to court or not. The results are presented in the Figure 6.

Figure 8: Taking medical negligence cases to courts

According to the findings in Figure 6, only 14.7% of respondents stated that the medical negligence cases they have been involved in or witnessed were taken to court. There seems to be a trend of claims of medical malpractice going unreported with the patients only sharing this kind of information in other forums other than the regulatory body of medical practitioners or the courts. This implies that here are many silent potential cases of medical malpractice which have not been addressed mainly because the victims either do not have confidence in the professional regulatory bodies or are scared of the procedures and complexities associated with the court process.

3.6. Current situation of medical negligence and malpractice issue

With the purpose of assessing the perception of the incidence of medical malpractices in Musanze District, respondents were asked to evaluate the current situation of the issue and the findings are presented in the Figure 7.

Figure 9: Current situation of medical negligence and malpractice

The findings in Figure 7 indicate that the majority of respondents, especially patients perceive the medical negligence and malpractice as a critical issue, considering that 8 of 20 interviewed patients (16% of all respondents) perceived it as very critical while as 46% of all categories of respondents perceived the problem critical. In recent years, the world has seen a sharp increase in medical malpractice litigation. It's estimated that 440,000 people are killed by medical errors every year, making it the third leading cause of death in the world, after heart disease and cancer. In other words, medical malpractice is responsible for 1,200 fatalities a day³².

In Rwanda, despite the act containing quite elaborate provisions on disciplinary measures, cases of medical malpractice have been on the increase in the recent past. Fifty three medical litigation cases were identified in Rwanda from 2008 to 2013. The recent example is the King Faisal Hospital and Kanombe Military hospital fined by Gasabo intermediate court for cutting off the breast of a patient after mistakenly diagnosing her with a level two cancer. The two national referral hospitals must pay the patient Rwf100 million (over US\$100,000) with immediate effect for what the court described as “medical negligence”. The verdict was delivered on Friday April 9, 2021 after an almost two-year legal battle⁴⁹.

3.7. Public awareness on medical negligence and malpractice

In 2013, the government, in consultation with its health sector partners, established the law No. 49/2012 elaborating medical service users’ rights and the responsibilities of health service providers. Unfortunately, most service users lack knowledge of their legal rights, which hinders improvement of service quality. This barrier to delivering quality services has been noted by several organizations, including the government of Rwanda. This section seeks to assess the level of public awareness, not only about their rights but also about the existing laws governing the problem.

3.7.1. Awareness about the right to medical care

The 1948 United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 25, says everyone has a right to a standard of living adequate for health and wellbeing, and it specifically mentions medical care. Awareness-raising can be an important part of developing community support for changes in the justice sector. Awareness changes knowledge and attitudes about law violation. This study sought to assess how aware are respondent about their rights to medical care and the findings are presented in the Figure 8.

Figure 10: Awareness about the rights to medical care

The finding in Figure 8 indicate that most of respondents are moderately aware about the rights to medical care (45% of all respondents) in addition to 25% of respondents who are very aware about the rights to medical care. Only 7.5% of respondents responded by “not aware at all”. This implies that the public is aware about the rights to medical care and thus, the severity of the issue of medical negligence and malpractice is due to other factors and these will be explored in further sections.

According to US Department of Justice (2000), educating the public is one of the most important strategies for preventing laws violation. People who know what actions they can take to reduce their risk of crime and how they can enhance neighborhood safety are the core of a safer community. By reminding people that a problem exists and showing them how they can address the problem, you enable them to take action⁵⁸.

⁵⁸ U.S. Department of Justice,2000.

3.7.2. Knowledge about the laws governing the medical negligence and malpractice

A public awareness and education is a way to bring a certain issue to the attention of a group of people and is a great way to highlight the need for crime prevention in the community. The important thing is to get key prevention information out to the target audience (medical practitioners and patients) and encourage them to take action in preventing or reducing law violation. This research sought to assess the level of awareness about the laws governing the medical negligence and malpractice among respondents and the findings are presented in the Figure 9.

Figure 11: Knowledge about the laws governing the medical negligence and malpractice

The findings in Figure 8 show that most of respondents (37.5%) especially the patients ignore the laws governing medical negligence and malpractice. This implies the majority of service users ignore the existing laws safeguarding their right and this may reduce the number of cases taken to courts of law. Ignorance of law is cited as the main reason for human rights violations.

3.8. Status of laws governing medical negligence and malpractice

In 2013, the government, in consultation with its health sector partners, established the law No. 49/2012, which instituted medical professional liability insurance. This law elaborates medical service users' rights and the responsibilities of health service providers. The Rwandan Constitution states that all citizens have the right and duties relating to health. This section assesses the respondents' perception about the strength and usage of existing laws governing the medical malpractice and negligence.⁵⁹

3.8.1. Strength of the laws governing the medical negligence and malpractice

With the aim of assessing the strength of existing laws, respondents operating in law enforcement were asked on how they perceive the robustness of existing laws and the findings are presented in figure 10.

Figure 12: Perceived robustness of laws governing the medical negligence and malpractice

⁵⁹ Art 41 of the Constitution of Republic of Rwanda.

The findings in Figure 10 suggest that the majority of respondents (60%) perceive the existing laws as weak. Moreover, these laws are perceived as very weak according to 10% of respondents. Only 30% of respondents perceived the laws governing medical negligence and malpractice in Rwanda as “strong”. The implication is that, even if the victims decide to take the case to court, the decision of court may be impeded by the weakness of the law in place and thus, unfavorable to victims.

According to Bizumuremyi⁶⁰, there is need for law reform regarding medical malpractice. For a health establishment to be held liable for damages under the vicarious liability principle, its physician must first be found to be in fault by an independent and impartial court. Filing a lawsuit against the health facility without suing the concerned professional will only lead to unjust decision either on the claimant or respondent. The concerned physician must be present in court and be given opportunity to defend themselves against claims of negligence. In awarding damages to the claimant patient, courts must have found negligence in the conduct of the physician. Damages should be based on the patient’s loss of opportunity and the claimant must prove this loss on balance of probability. Courts should also stick to awarding damages on principle of established liability rather than awarding ex-gratia damages.

3.8.2. Usage of existing laws in case of medical negligence and malpractice

As per the finding in previous sections (Section 4.6, Figure 7), malpractice and negligence cases have been found to be increasing. Thus, the existing laws should be applied. With the aim of assessing the status of usage of existing laws, respondents were asked on how they perceive the robustness of existing laws and the findings are presented in figure 11.

⁶⁰ Bizumuremyi Isaac, 2021.

Figure 13: How often are existing laws applied in case of medical negligence and malpractice.

The findings in Figure 11 indicate that the majority of respondents (74%) think that the existing laws are rarely applied in case of medical negligence and malpractice. Only 4% of all respondents think the laws governing medical negligence and malpractice are always applied. This suggests that most of the claims of medical malpractice go unreported.

According to The New Times, people hear of few medical-related cases in Rwandan courts. A number of them are managed by the medical council and penalties meted out include deregistration, and suspension for varying periods. The main challenge faced while adjudicating cases of medical malpractice in Rwanda is establishing the level of responsibility and the level at which the medical care provided to a patient was below minimum required standards.⁶¹

⁶¹ The New Times, August 30,2013

3.9. Factors contributing to medical malpractice and negligence

With the purpose of assessing the perceived factors contributing the increase of medical negligence and malpractice, respondents were asked to list the main factors and the findings are presented in figure 12.

Figure 14: Perceived factors favoring the medical negligence and malpractice

The findings in Figure 12 indicate that the main factor contributing the medical negligence and malpractice is the “scarcity of medical practitioners” (90%) followed by “other health priorities” (80%). These two are interlinked given that if medical practitioners were enough, all health issues would be considered as priorities. The poor training of practitioners was found to be contributing at 54%, followed by law deficit (50%) and public ignorance (46%) respectively.

According to the Rwanda Medical and Dental Council (RMDC) data, the newly deployed doctors add on the existing list of 1,176 general practitioners and 495 specialists in different fields considering an estimated population of almost 12 million, Rwanda counts an average of one doctor per 12,000 people.

Though the ministry hails the significant increase of medical personnel in the country international standards show that there is still a pressing need for quantity and quality of health professionals to ensure delivery of quality health services.

Another factor that contributes to malpractice is that medical practitioners are often beset by other health policy priorities, which can relegate patients' rights to a secondary or even tertiary concern⁴⁴. HIV/AIDS, malaria, Covid19, swine flu, and other infectious diseases plague countries like India, China, and many African nations.

3.10. Effects of medical negligence and malpractice on victims

With the intention of assessing the impact of medical negligence and malpractice on victims, respondents were asked to list the main effects and the findings are presented in figure 13.

Figure 15: Perceived effects of medical negligence and malpractice on victims

The findings in Figure 13 show that the main perceived effect of the medical negligence and malpractice on victims is the “loss of trust in medical practitioners” (100%) followed by “condition worsening” (90%), defensive medicine (62%) and psychological damages (20%).

Medical malpractice can negatively affect all aspects of an injured patient’s life, from physical and emotional damages to serious financial hardships. When death is the result of medical negligence, “the surviving dependents or beneficiaries may be entitled to monetary damages in order to help pay for medical costs and other expenses incurred by the family of the victim. Medical malpractice affects both patients and physicians severely⁶²

3.11. Mitigation measures

After the assessment of the current situation and factors contributing to medical negligence and evaluating the effects on victims, this study sought to know how the issue may be addressed and respondents were asked about what they perceive as mitigation measures. The findings are presented in Figure 14.

Figure 16: Perceived mitigation measures for medical negligence and malpractice on victims

⁶² Jonathan, T., 2010

According to findings in Figure 14, the most frequently perceived solution would be “the effort by medical practitioners to reduce harm” (74%) followed by “awareness campaign” (62%), “improved communication” (62%) and “law enforcement” (28%).

Reference made to the report by Taarifa Rwanda⁴⁹, any long-term solution must encompass methods of reducing injuries to patients and at the same time changing the system from defense of the physician to compensation of the patient. If such changes are not forthcoming, physicians will become uninsurable and the private practice of medicine as we now know it will disappear in this country

CHAPTER 4: GENERAL CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. General Conclusions

The general background established that the cases of medical malpractice have been on the increase in the recent past and the problem statement revealed that there is lack of information as to the procedure to follow when a medical negligence complaint happens within the health facilities. The governing and monitoring medical bodies exist but they are not efficiently assisting victims and thus, four research questions were formulated along with according hypothesis and specific objectives.

The conceptual and theoretical framework related to medical negligence and malpractice were reviewed to respond to research questions and achieve the research objectives and have revealed that the case of negligence are increasing. The factors contributing to medical negligence and malpractice were explored and the solutions to medical malpractice were reviewed. With the aim of enriching the review, four negligence cases were studied and the related legal framework was reviewed.

The research methodology used questionnaire survey for primary data collection where purposive sampling was used primary and secondary data and collected data were analyzed by using Microsoft excel package and in accordance with the research objectives, the following conclusions were drawn from findings of this study:

- The current situation of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze District is critical. The findings in Figure 7 indicate that the majority of respondents, especially patients perceive the medical negligence and malpractice as a critical issue, considering that 8 of 20 interviewed patients (16% of all respondents) perceived it as very critical while as 46% of all categories of respondents perceived the problem critical.
- The finding in Figure 8 indicate that most of respondents are moderately aware about the rights to medical care (45% of all respondents) in addition to 25% of respondents who are very aware about the rights to medical care. Only 7.5% of respondents responded by “not aware at all”.

- The main factor contributing the medical negligence and malpractice is the “scarcity of medical practitioners” (90%) followed by “other health priorities” (80%). The poor training of practitioners was found to be contributing at 54%, followed by law deficit (50%) and public ignorance (46%) respectively (Figure 12).
- The most frequently perceived solution to medical negligence and malpractice would be “the effort by medical practitioners to reduce harm” (74%) followed by “awareness campaign” (62%), “improved communication” (62%) and “law enforcement” (28%), (Figure 12)

4.2. Recommendations

On the basis of the study objectives, study results and literature reviewed, the following recommendations were made:

- There should be further researches on medical negligence
- The monitoring and regulation organs and bodies should be empowered
- The education and awareness campaigns about the existing laws governing medical negligence and malpractice should be organized
- The Government of Rwanda should increase the number of Physicians, Nurses, Midwives and allied health practitioners in all health facilities.
- The medical practitioners should be trained on how to reduce harm to patients.
- More clear and strong laws governing medical negligence and malpractice should be established

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APPENDIX

Appendix: Results tables

Table 2: Gender Distribution among respondents

Respondent category	Male		Female	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Health Practitioners	12	24%	8	16%
Patients	8	16%	12	24%
Law Practitioners and law enforcement agents	5	10%	5	10%
Total	25	50%	25	50%

Table 3: Age Distribution

Respondent category	20-30 Years		31-50		51-Above	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Health Practitioners	4	8%	11	22%	5	10%
Patients	6	12%	10	20%	4	8%
Law Practitioners and law enforcement agents	1	2%	7	14%	2	4%
Total	11	22%	38	56%	11	22%

Table 4: Working experience among respondents

Respondent category	Below 5 Years		5-10 Years		11-Above	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Health Practitioners	2	6.6%	6	20%	12	40%
Law Practitioners and law enforcement agents	3	10%	2	6.6%	5	16.6%
Total	5	16.6%	8	26.6%	17	56.6%

Table 5: Involvement, witnessing or dealing with medical negligence and/or malpractice

Respondent category	Yes		No	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Health Practitioners	18	36%	2	4%
Patients	16	32%	4	8%
Law Practitioners and law enforcement agents	10	20%	0	0%

Total	44	88%	6	12%
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Table 6: Taking cases to courts

Respondent category	Yes		No		Don't know	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Health Practitioners	3	8.8%	14	41.2%	1	2.9%
Patients	2	5.9%	12	35.3%	2	5.9%
Total	5	14.7%	16	76.5%	3	8.8%

Table 7: Current situation and extent of medical negligence and malpractice

Respondent category	Very Critical		Critical		Slightly Critical		Not Critical at all	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>
Health Practitioners	3	6%	10	20%	5	10%	2	4%
Patients	8	16%	8	16%	3	6%	1	2%
Law Practitioners and law enforcement agents	1	2%	5	10%	2	4%	2	4%
Total	12	24%	23	46%	10	20%	5	10%

Table 8: Awareness about the rights to medical care

Respondent category	Very aware		Moderately aware		Slightly aware		Not aware at all	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>
Health Practitioners	7	17.5%	8	20%	4	10%	1	2.5%
Patients	3	7.5%	10	25%	5	12.5%	2	5%
Total	10	25%	18	45%	9	22.5%	3	7.5%

Table 9: Knowledge about the laws governing the medical negligence and malpractice

Respondent category	Yes		No		Some what	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>
Health Practitioners	12	30%	2	5%	6	15%
Patients	2	5%	13	32.5%	5	12.5%

Total	14	2.5%	15	37.5%	11	27.5%
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Table 10: Strength of the laws governing the medical negligence and malpractice

Respondent category	Strong		Weak		Very Weak	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>
Law Practitioners and law enforcement agents	3	30%	60	5%	1	10%

Table 11: Usage of the laws in case of medical negligence and malpractice

Respondent category	Always		Sometimes		Rarely	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>
Health Practitioners	0	0%	5	10%	15	30%
Patients	2	4%	4	8%	14	28%
Law Practitioners and law enforcement agents	0	0%	2	4%	8	16%

Table 12: Factors contributing to medical malpractice and negligence

Factors	Respondents (All)	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Scarcity of medical practitioners	45	90%
Other Health Priorities	40	80%
Poor Training of medical practitioners	27	54%
Law Deficits	25	50%
Unawareness /Ignorance	23	46%

Table 13: Effects of medical negligence and malpractice on victims

Factors	Respondents (All)	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Loss of trust in practitioners	50	100%
Condition worsening	43	86%
Defensive medicine	31	62%
Death	25	50%
Psychological damages	10	20%

Table 14: Mitigation measures

Measures	Respondents (All)	
	Frequency	Percentage
Efforts by physicians to reduce harm	37	74%
Awareness campaigns	31	62%
Improve communication with patients	30	60%
Law enforcement	14	28%

Appendix 2: Questionnaire

I am Rosine Ishimwe, a Bachelors Candidate in Law, at University of Kigali. As a part of my dissertation, I am doing a research on the status of medical negligence and malpractice in Musanze district, Rwanda and some information can only be provided by health practitioners, patients and law enforcement agents. I would be really thankful if you could spend some time, taking part of this survey. Everything mentioned in the survey is just for the academic study and your answers will only be used for the research purposes.

Thank You,

Rosine Ishimwe

Section A: Biography

1. Date
2. Respondent name Sex Age....
3. Health Facility.....
4. Education level.....

5. Strata of Respondent (a)Health practitioner, (b)Nurse, (c)Customers, (d)Law enforcement agency (RIB, Police, Lawyer, Court)
6. Other.....

Section B: Interview Questions Interview questions for Health Practitioners and Patients

1. Do you know what Medical malpractice and negligence means?

Yes	
No	

2. How long have you been working as health practitioner?

More than 10 years	
5-10 Years	
Less than 5 Years	

3. Have you ever been involved or witnessed medical malpractice?

Yes	
No	

If yes, was the case taken to court?

Yes	
No	
Don't know	

4. How would you qualify the current situation/extent of medical malpractice issue?

a	Very Critical	
b	Critical	
c	Slightly Critical	
d	Not Critical at all	

5. Are there any laws regulating medical negligence and malpractice?

Yes	
No	
Don't know	

6. How aware are medical service users for their lights?

a	Very Aware	
b	Moderately aware	
d	Slightly aware	
e	Not aware at all	

7. How often do victims use the existing laws and regulations?

a	Always	
b	Sometimes	
c	Rarely	
d	Never	

7. What are the factors contributing to medical malpractice and negligence?

a	Scarcity of Physicians	
b	Other Health Priorities	
c	Poor Training	
d	Regulatory Deficits	
e	Unawareness among patients	

8. What are the effects of medical malpractices on patients?

a	Socio-economic damages	
b	Psychological damages	
c	Defensive medicine	
d	Loss of trust in practitioners	
e	Condition worsening	
f	Death	

9. What do you think needs to be done to address medical malpractice and negligence?

a	Efforts by physicians to reduce harm	
b	Improve communication with patients	
c	Increase awareness about patients' lights	
d	Law enforcement	

Thank you!

Sect C: Interview Questions for law enforcement agents

1. How long have you been working in law enforcement field?

a	More than 10 years	
b	5-10 Ears	
c	Less than 5 Years	

2. How strong are the laws and regulations governing medical negligence and malpractice in Rwanda?

a	Strong	
b	Weak	
c	Very weak	

3. Have you ever dealt with malpractice case?

a	Yes	
b	No	

4. How often do victims use the existing laws and regulations

a	Always	
b	Sometimes	
c	Rarely	
d	Never	

5. What are the factors contributing to medical malpractice and negligence?

a	Scarcity of Physicians	
b	Other Health Priorities	
c	Poor Training	
d	Regulatory Deficits	
e	Unawareness among patients	

6. What are the effects of medical malpractices on patients

a	Socio-economic damages	
b	Psychological damages	
c	Defensive medicine	
d	Loss of trust in practitioners	
e	Condition worsening	
f	Death	

7. What do you think needs to be done to address medical malpractice and negligence?

a	Efforts by physicians to reduce harm	
b	Improve communication with patients	
c	Increase awareness about patients' rights	
d	Law enforcement	

Thank you!